

A Deeper Look into Wild Horse Management
in the United States

A Proposal for Humane and Sustainable Practices

Sandra Alcini

Environmental Sciences

Professor Smita Malpani

WCC

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Wild horses in the Western United States are left vulnerable to threats by humans and industry, including from those who are charged to protect them. The ranching industry is compromising wild horse communities and the public lands on which they live under auspices of the federal government (SOWH, 2022). Wild horse extermination and privatization of public land is normalized in America even though many people dislike what is happening.

The history of wild horses is confusing and causes additional conflict about wild horse management on public land. The US government often calls for the removal of wild horses, calling them invasive, and prioritizes ranching for cattle or sheep (AWHC, 2021). Ranchers and the agricultural industry have encouraged a public bias against horses since the first Europeans settled in the West (explanation forthcoming). The Wild Free Ranging Horses and Burros Act (WFRHBA) of 1971 was enacted to protect American wild horses (AWH) and burros, but the Bureau of Land Management (BLM, the Bureau) which is highly staffed by ranchers and supporters of the agricultural industry, has total control of the WFRHBA. The Bureau directs sizable amounts of taxpayer money through transactions involving public land and agriculture, and it appears that the government views AWH and their habitat as their commodity (San Benito Realty, BLM, 2023).

The incomplete history of AWH and confusing taxonomy, *Equus caballus ferus*, have been major obstacles in getting protection for AWH (The Cloud Foundation, 2022) that would exceed the power of the BLM. Many Americans appropriate funds and other support for protection of AWH from capture or wrongful death, but the power dynamic surrounding the Bureau's management does not prioritize the horses' well-being (Malone, 2022). Instead, the Bureau focuses on the money that is generated by extracting horses from their natural habitat (CBS4, 2022). AWH are being killed and imprisoned at such an alarming rate that the Bureau itself is overwhelmed with the situation and has begun outsourcing management of captured horses to select private land owners (BLM, 2021).

This thesis critically examines the current management of American Wild Horses (AWH) in the United States. Quantitative data and anthropological narratives attesting to human relationships with AWH are used to explain AWH history, taxonomy, and an early American social construction of wildness in land management. A review follows regarding the infrastructure and current practices of the Bureau of Land Management (BLM). In closing, recommendations are suggested to improve the care, population management, and sustainability of AWH and their habitat.

Are Mustangs wild or feral? And why does this matter?

Phylogeny and Genetics of Equus Caballus

AWH of today are commonly called Mustangs. Due to the horse taxonomy *Equus caballus ferus*, most people believe that Mustangs are not only Spanish, but are also domesticated animals that have escaped. (A feral animal is one that was once domesticated and has now escaped.) While this was historically true in some instances, it is debatable whether wild horses went extinct in North America and what that could mean for the wild horse.

Wild horses originated in North America and migrated all over the world by crossing the Bering Land Bridge from Alaska (MacPhee, 2023)(Taylor, 2023). After many years of allowing travel back and forth, the land bridge was eventually overtaken by water. The horse populations on either side were then kept separate, and through natural selection there were slight amounts of divergent evolution in the different populations, but not enough to create a new species (Mac Phee, 2023). All horses that exist today are still, amazingly, the same species. There are subspecies like the Przewalski Horse, *Equus caballus przewalski*, but they are still the same species and able to interbreed and produce fertile offspring (MacPhee, 2023).

Until recently, scientists and academia have unquestionably believed in the extinction of *Equus* in North America around 12,000 years ago during the ice age. A team of paleontologists from New York, however, recently identified “a lingering signal of *Equus sp.* (North American Horse) and *Mammuthus primigenius* (wooly mammoth) at multiple sites persisting thousands of years after (*Equus*)’ supposed extinction from the

fossil record” (Murchie, 2021). Their recent work builds on a previous discovery of horse sedimentary DNA (sedaDNA) that was unexpectedly discovered in permafrost in the Yukon and “post-dates the last macrofossil evidence of (the horse) in Alaska by 3300 years” (Murchie 2021). This indicates a cryptic, or ghost, population of horses in North America that have otherwise not yet been discovered. The same team of scientists found an “appearance of *Equus* and *Mammuthus* sedaDNA as late as ca. 6000 ca BP” (Murchie, 2021).

Through DNA sequencing, scientists have determined that many grazers lived symbiotically in North America after the ice age. They have also determined that the forage changed around the same time that *Homo sapien*, or human, biomarkers began to appear (Murchie, 2014). With the change in forage, scientists believe that the grazing community changed as well, but they can only speculate about why the change in grazers coincided with the arrival of humans (Murchie, 2014).

The Harrington horse, *Harrington hipus francesci*, commonly called the Stilt-Legged Horse, was it’s own genus very close to *Equus* that was also discovered in North America but was long extinct (Stephans, 2017). The Stilt-Legged horse had the same markings as the ancient Przewalski horse that is now endangered in Asia. The striped pattern and other primitive markings appear in American wild and domestic horses carrying “wild-type” genetics for the dun phenotype. Non-dun1 (one gene in a family of dun genetics) gene expression looks especially close to the Przewalski. The non-dun1 gene is over 40,000 years old (Imsland, 2015).

The following Maximum Likelihood Tree shows one clade in Equid phylogeny, this clade, Clade A, “was broadly distributed from central Europe to North America north and south of the ice. . . Most or even all of North American *caballines* were members of the same species (Weinstock, 2015).

Phylogeny of Recent and Pleistocene Equids

The maximum likelihood tree was constructed with two fragments of the mitochondrial control region (583 bp and 133 bp in the HVR1 and HVR2 regions, respectively). Bayesian analysis produced a similar topology. The general time-reversible substitution model was used in both techniques. Black numbers above/beside nodes are posterior probabilities and bootstrap values, respectively (only values > 50% are shown). White numbers on black background are divergence times as calculated from the molecular data. Numbers/letters in bold at the beginning of each specimen's name are sample numbers or GenBank accession numbers. Labels of prehistoric specimens are followed by their age, if available, in thousands of years. The outgroup (Rhinoceros and Ceratotherium) is not shown. (Weinstock 2015)
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In a newly published article, Taylor et al. detail the genetics of American horses and their relationships with various groups of Indigenous people in the early 1600s. Taylor's team of anthropologists blended physical science and sociology for this study, and for the first time, a team of European Americans and Indigenous people worked together to tell the story of the North American horse.

“We conducted an interdisciplinary study of an assemblage of historic archaeological horse remains, integrating genomic, isotopic, radiocarbon, and paleopathological evidence. Archaeological and modern North American horses show strong Iberian genetic affinities... This ancestry was, however, not exclusive to historic or modern North American horses but instead shared across most Eurasian lineages, including a ~4000-year-old horse from Iberia, a ~5100-year-old horse from western Beringia, and several ancient domestic specimens such as a 1447 to 1621 CE sample from Iran (Belgheis). Therefore, the minor ancestry component detected likely reflects multiple ancient contacts between Eurasia and North America through the Beringian land bridge during the past 830,000 years, in line with previously reported studies (*Virshinina, 2021*) and also apparent in mitochondrial phylogenies (Fig. 2B)*.

—Taylor et al., 2023

Their findings support the studies of both Murchie and Collin, and add a relational component to the history of humans and horses in 17th century North America. “The Lakota peoples strove to cultivate their environment and adapt their lifeways to ensure that *Šungwakan* ([Lakota] *Sacred Companion*) could live aligned with its natural systems. Within this nation-to-nation alliance, the horse enhanced the abilities of the Lakota with regard to hunting, mobility, healing, and more (Hunska, 2023). Therefore, for the Lakota peoples, saying ‘our horse’ never reflects ownership but rather responsibility for a sacred relative” (Taylor, 2023).

*See appendix *i* for Figure 2B

History of the Horse

Horses were first domesticated around 2200 years BCE in the Pontic-Caspian Steppes, Northern Caucasus. (Orlando 2021) Domesticated horses quickly spread throughout Europe and China, and eventually to Africa. Domestication of the horse overtook all wild horses during this time except for the Przewalski horse, which is perhaps why all other horses are now called domestic, or labeled using taxonomy as *ferus*. (Leinaweaver, 2022) Christopher Columbus carried domesticated horses on his second voyage from Spain to Hispaniola (now called The Dominican Republic), and Hernan Cortez brought the horses from Hispaniola to Brazil in 1519. Following the traditional academic belief that all horses had become extinct in North America 12,000 years ago, most people believe wild horses that live in America today are feral descendants of the Spanish horses brought by Columbus and Cortez (Pestor, Bradford, 2021)(Mitchell, 2015).

Scholars disagree though (Collin, 2017), and believe that is a Eurocentric myth used dismissively towards the Indigenous people of the Americas to further degrade their status and credibility to provide for themselves or to own anything of European “value.” Through oral history, the Lakota say that each Lakota (Dakota, Nakota) person rose from the earth with a pony as two halves to a whole. (Big Eagle, 2023). Indigenous oral history is filled with countless stories of ancestors and horses.

The idea that horses could have declined to a very small population rather than to extinction with the onset of human migration to North America is entirely plausible. New information from Taylor et al. supports the possibility that the purported cryptic horse populations (Murchie, 2021) were enhanced by the horses brought from Spain in the 16th century suggesting that it was, in fact, a reunion of horses rather than a reintroduction (Collin, 2017).

In an extensive dissertation from University of Alaska at Fairbanks, Yvette Running Horse Collin shares many stories about sacred connections between horses

and Indigenous people. She also uses South American artifacts from the Incan and Mayan peoples to show human connections to the horse that predate the arrival of Spain in the Americas (Photos from dissertation shown below).

Figure 4 A Horseman Petroglyph at Alto de Pitis, Peru.³⁷⁰

Figure 9 Representation of a Horse in Mayan Temple.³⁹⁰

Horses are unequivocally bonded into Indigenous culture and considered sacred relatives. Horses have healing abilities and bring messages to humans in dreams. Horses carry sacred medicine and form deep bonds with humans. This is seen on the modern day range between wild horse photographers and their herd. It's called a "heart horse," which seems fitting because horses certainly have power to heal the human heart.

Photo by Sandy Sharkey

“...The explanation that I have been exposed to...in my academic education, it just doesn't fit with the patterns that I see elsewhere in the world. It makes little sense that ...all Native People, all over the Americas contributed to hunting the horse to extinction. Likewise, seeing the capacity for horses to exist in Arctic environments and in desert environments and so forth, it seemed unlikely that climate change could have caused all horses in all of the Americas to go extinct and yet not in Eurasia and Africa. Likewise, I think that ... [if] a disease infected and wiped out all of the horses in America, from Alaska to Tierra del Fuego, then where's the evidence? Where's the physical evidence? That shouldn't be hard to find in fossilized and other remains of horses. There should be an obvious movement of equine death that can be seen in the archeological and geological record...I'm not saying it's not there, but I have never come across it in anything I have read or any people I've talked to about this. And so, I came to the conclusion that well, Europeans landed in the Americas knowing that horses were power. And so immediately began to take control of horse herds...”

—Koskey, 2016 (Collin, 2017)

Three mounted Comanche warriors, 1892 (Weiser, 2021)

Things become confusing with academic books like *Black Elk Speaks*, a popular book written by an American writer and poet who had interest in the early American settlement and narrated Black Elk's stories in English. In the book, Black Elk says that his people didn't ride horses until the white man arrived. This could be true, or it could be misinterpreted. Black Elk did not speak English, nor did he read English, so we can only trust that this is accurate. The other considerable factor is that the horses could have existed without being ridden, much like the buffalo, the elk, and the antelope. And yet another possibility is that horses could've been used by some people and not by others. Before colonization, Indigenous people didn't use written language the way Europeans did, and there are no books written by, or from the perspective of, Indigenous peoples until the late 1800s and after colonial assimilation, so we cannot safely compare the two.

The history of the horse is still unfolding. The above-referenced paleontological evidences are newly presented and are not yet common knowledge. Yvette Running Horse Collin's dissertation is becoming more accepted as new scientific evidence is published in support of her work. The history of the horse in America has been misunderstood and overlooked by agriculturalists and academia since the dawn of European colonization (Taylor, 2023). Further, the taxonomy of the horse using the name *ferus*, is presumptuous and misrepresentative (Leinaweaver, 2022). As new evidence is presented, the taxonomy of *Equus* would benefit from change with respect to new information to further eliminate this confusion.

Why does this matter?

A lot of Americans are unaware that American land is not pristine, and they are wary of invasive species that will "alter" the pristine landscape. The land, however, has already been drastically changed more than once, especially with the removal of the long-time communities of wolves, humans, and thousands of grazers. The very idea of "pristine" is flawed in that humans have altered the land for millennia. Forward to the 21st century, and "there is hardly an acre out there that isn't affected by livestock, mining, oil, hunting, or recreational uses" (Hellyer 2023). A lot of Americans

understandably want to protect what is left of “preserved” lands and keep them as healthy as possible. With the false narrative that the horses who live on US public lands are an escaped invasive species, wild horses are disliked by American purists.

Poorly understood American history constructs the harmful narrative that AWH are destructive and don't belong on American land, yet horses have lived in North America for almost 60 million years. There are about 5000 years with no paleontological record of horses (5K years is .008% of 60M). Paleontology shows that they could have been here, but no absolute proof exists either way. Genus *Equus* originated in North America, and the species that exists now is the same species as the horses who were here thousands of years ago. Further, AWH in the West seem to have evolved very well to live with the land. It's noteworthy that *Hominids* originated in Africa, so it's ironic that *Equids* which originated in North America, are considered invasive by a taxonomic family from another continent.

The agricultural sector has labelled AWH as a feral, invasive species, and the horses are constructed as a pest or an infestation on otherwise pristine lands. In actuality, AWH are a naturally occurring species that prefer the same forage as cattle, a non-native, genetically modified species, grown as a commodity by ranchers. When left to their natural rhythms, AWH and other native species like buffalo, big horned sheep, and antelope use niche partitioning, otherwise called “rotational grazing” which allows the native forage to regenerate without intervention (Fynn, 2016). Cattle ranchers ignore this amazing natural process and prefer planting monocultures which creates consistency for their agricultural product (SOWH, 2022). As a result, the Bureau regularly targets AWH for removal in favor of growing cattle (Fedak, 2022).

The BLM claims that removed “feral” horses will be adopted and domesticated (BLM), but AWH are wild animals. Wildness is naturally selected over many generations, and a wild animal cannot be domesticated in one lifetime. Domestication of any animal takes many generations over thousands of years (Daly 2019). At most, an adopter could tame the horse, but it would not become domestic. Classifying AWH

as a native species would henceforth make them wild rather than feral, and they could be protected under the Endangered Species Act. Another option is classification as a Naturalized Species as they've done with the Sable Island Horses in Canada (Gov't of Canada, 2022).

The Early American Social Construction of Wildness

The Cowboy Mentality

The early days of the American Frontier conceived a dichotomy of ideas between wildness and progress in the West. Early settlers saw wildness as something to be conquered, and domestication was the means to that end. When settlers first saw the American Frontier, they envisioned their own domestic enterprise within the “pristine” landscape without considering it was already inhabited by humans. The current inhabitants though, among them the Indigenous people, weren’t living in wildness, nor did they indulge in the concept of domestication (Standing Bear, 1908). The landscape, at this time, was actually a complex society living in symbiosis with

nature. Without consideration for existing culture, the European settlers saw the land as wild and unclaimed. Bringing ideas from Europe, the settlers imposed domestication on the land and saw this as rewardable progress.

The Indigenous people and animals, conversely saw not the land as wild, but the European settlers as wild in a different sense of the word (Standing Bear, 1908). The settlers appeared unruly, unclean, and uncivilized. So here, a dichotomy exists within wildness itself that over hundreds of years, led to many battles and tragic events like Little Big Horn and the Battle/Massacre at Wounded Knee. When the Indigenous people were overcome, wildness of the land was lost. Wildness in the sense of pristine complexity within nature was now considered uncivilized and would eventually be considered an obstacle that does nothing but block the progress of domestication (Penrose, 2014).

The setting of the American Frontier created a niche for the American Cowboy. With complete freedom over the open West, the cowboy became the anti-hero achieving wholeness in the dichotomy of wildness as a facilitator of progress. Domestication became synonymous with progress as America spread westward. The cultural fascination with capturing the wild and transforming it placed most people outside of nature (Penrose, 2014), and the construction of living symbiotically with the land was considered primitive, uncultured, and weak. Agriculture was the “American dream” of the 1800s.

When Jefferson doubled the size of the nation by purchasing the Louisiana Territory from France in 1803—thus extending the western frontier from the Appalachians across the Mississippi to the Rocky Mountains—he proposed to Congress the (Indigenous peoples) should be encouraged to settle down on smaller tracts and do farming. “Two measures are deemed expedient. First to encourage them to abandon hunting...Secondly, to Multiply trading houses among them... leading them thus to agriculture, to manufactures, and civilization....”

Jefferson’s talk of “agriculture... manufactures... civilization is crucial.” (Indigenous) removal was necessary for the opening of the vast

American lands to agriculture, to commerce, to markets, to money, to the development of the modern capitalist economy. Land was indispensable for all this, and after the Revolution, huge tracts of land were bought up by rich speculators, including George Washington and Patrick Henry. John Donelson, a North Carolina surveyor, ended up with twenty thousand acres of land near what is now Chattanooga. His son-in-law made twenty-two trips out of Nashville in 1795 for land deals. This was Andrew Jackson.

—Howard Zinn, *A People's History*, 1980

While some of the Indigenous people accepted assimilation and were given land, tools, and cattle, others chose to remain in nature which historically did not fare well (Zinn, 1980). By the end of the 19th century, the Indigenous people who did not assimilate were **“duly confined to small reserves, where, according to government policy, they would be protected and civilized in preparation for their assimilation into the new Euro-(based) society.”** (Penrose, 2014) With Indigenous people effectively sequestered, settlers could easily portray their culture as part of the past. The Indigenous were given a new identity in the new world: an identity of lacking culture and education and unable to get a job or provide for themselves. The suppression of Indigenous culture brought a reification of wildness as an inferiority in America (Penrose, 2014).

This new dichotomy now constructed nature and wildness as the enemy of progress. With a new transcontinental railroad, more settlers moved west, cities formed, and fences went up. With fenced property lines stretching across the range, transporting cattle became easier by train than by horse. The era of the open frontier was over, and many cowboys were out of a job. There was a new hierarchy in the West, starting with Ranch Owner and moving on down to Seasonal Help (Wortham).

Even the cowboys were no longer wild, striving to own land while the “lowly” wranglers, many of them Indigenous people, were cast out as drifters in this new social construction (Wortham). Years later with the invention of radio, the beloved cowboy era was recreated as entertainment. The eventual introduction of television brought

stars like Gene Autry, Roy Rogers, and the Lone Ranger who entertained an entire generation of Baby boomers that had never actually seen a real cowboy or the open frontier. The cowboy construction became that of an amicable “good man...often merged with that of the lawman (Wortham).” The cowboy construct became a trend and a social norm. Onscreen programming almost always portrayed the cowboy as the hero, and Indigenous people, being the other half of the dichotomy, were merged with the antithetical villain, hence the popular construct of “cowboys and indians” which further perpetuated the domestic/wild dichotomy (Penrose, 2014, Wortham).

By the early 20th century, humans were successfully divided by race, and grazing animals were seen as chattel (Penrose, 2014, Zinn, 1980). The United States now had a normative description of race, and a social prescription solidified nature as property to be conquered while race determined the conquerer (Penrose, 2014). Lawmakers and other Gilded Age Populists (Stewart, 2023) had by now massacred the buffalo in a well-known effort to erase Indigenous people (Washburn, 2022). They began killing wolves who were considered competition of the new apex, the American rancher. Horses were employed by ranchers, and with the drought of the 1890's (Stewart, 2023), many horses and burros were discarded or escaped to wild herds. With so little left wild and the failing agricultural economy, the AWH became the new anti-hero, admired by conservationists for their wildness (Spring River Wild Horse Management Group, SRWHMG, 2022) and hunted by agriculturalists for food and to eliminate competition for livestock (SRWHMG, 2022). “By the twentieth century, horses and burros roaming free on the nation’s remaining rangelands were more valuable for their meat than their labor” (Childers, 2021).

1927 AZ newspaper, photo courtesy of Salt River Wild Horse Management Group, 2022

Descendants of 19th century cowboys and ranching barons have carried these ideas into the present. Most of the western ranch owners in the 21st century are 4th or 5th generation ranchers and openly dislike AWH. Most ranchers support elimination of wildlife in favor of agricultural progress, and culls for different wild species continue each year in the interest of livestock ranching (Robbins 2023, French, 2023). One can argue in either direction that the westward expansion of the United States was progress or extermination, but the fact remains that the social construction of wildness as an obstacle to progress exists, and it is systemically prevalent in America today.

How does this construction of wildness effect the management of AWH?

Oddly, horses aren't fully considered wildlife or livestock, but rather their classification changes depending on the situation (TRNP, BLM, 2023). Wild horses have always been a target for theft and murder since they didn't fall under any jurisdiction of protection until the WFRHBA. AWH populations are continuously threatened with extermination by federal offices like the BLM, National Park Service, and US Forest Service. The WFRHBA is the only protection available to wild horses which prevents anyone except the federal government from harassing, branding, or killing them, and it has been altered so many times by the BLM, that it barely resembles its original form (BLM, 1971, 2023). There are no checks and balances with this system. The BLM alters the WFRHBA as they please, and further, they have the ability to file a Permanent Instruction Memorandum at will to supersede any recent documents.

“Public lands possess energy resources, and the Mustang herds complicate the extraction of these resources.” (Dalke, 2010) Last year alone, 7,979 AWH were “rounded up” from public lands (BLM 2023). AWH habitats on public land are diminishing for cattle ranching, oil, and to collect minerals like magnesium from the magnesium deposits in Utah (McKay, 2020). The 7,979 horses captured in 2022 have been warehoused with over 100K other formerly wild horses who are **“duly confined**

to small reserves, where, according to government policy, they would be protected and civilized in preparation for their assimilation into the new Euro-(based) society.” (Penrose, 2014)(BLM, 2022) While some of the captured horses will be moved into long term holding pastures, many will die in holding from injury or disease, and most will be jettisoned into the auction pipeline (AWHC, 2023). For FY2022, the appropriation for BLM management of wild horses and burros was \$137.1 million (CRS, 2022). This number does not include money acquired for grazing permits, public land sales, or leases.

The Bureau of Land Management, US Interior

The BLM is a federal agency and an integration of two 19th century offices: The Grazing Commission and the General Land Office. Both offices formed during American westward expansion to encourage agricultural use of land. The foundational offices were essentially a continuation of 19th century associations like the Farmers’ Alliance (Stewart, 2023) and the Wyoming Stock Grower’s Association (WSGA) (Davis, 2014). The Farmers’ Alliance became popular by offering exclusive benefits to their members when the agriculture industry was failing in the 1890’s. (Stewart, 2023), and the WSGA was a group of wealthy cattle barons and land heirs in Cheyenne, WY.

The WSGA became infamously known as “The Invaders” of the Johnson County Range War of 1892. The cattle barons realized they could make profits from growing cows and overstocked their land (The First Contradiction of Capitalism and a rudimentary mistake). After a hard year in ranching and a huge loss of inventory (cattle), The Invaders rode north to Buffalo from Cheyenne to hang 70 small-town cattle ranchers who were successfully raising herds of up to 400 cattle. They had originally accused the Buffalo ranchers of stealing their cows and sent two hitmen who unsuccessfully tried to kill a popular rancher in Buffalo. Consequently, this rancher testified in court against them. Out of fear of incrimination, The Invaders rode north to Buffalo, set fire to a barn where the rancher was hiding, and shot the man as he escaped the fire. The Invaders were later arrested; however, no charges were ever filed. (Davis, 2014)

Leaders of the Bureau have traditionally been multigenerational ranchers and heirs of farmland that was acquired in the 1800's. Errol Rice, for instance, Executive Director turned "Ranch Liaison," is a "5th generation Montanan cattle rancher" and sells insurance to commercial ranchers in the agricultural industry (ranchersinsurance.com). Deb Haaland is the current Secretary of the US Interior and head of the BLM. Haaland is also from a ranching (and military) background and is married to multimillionaire cattle rancher, Skip Sayre. Most of the staff are ranchers, and many have earned college degrees studying agriculture. Admittedly, under Haaland's current leadership, the Interior appears to have shifted slightly toward a more balanced staff including Chuck Sams, an amicable Indigenous leader, and a long list of new graduates from non-agricultural backgrounds. However, change in the Bureau, if any, has been minimal.

The US Interior and the BLM, view nature as an economic commodity in need of stewardship. Preservation of nature falls into the wrong side of the wildness versus progress dichotomy. Under the aforementioned social construction, preservation, especially of AWH, is not a priority to the BLM, especially when they process over \$100M per year by removing AWH from their natural habitat. They claim it is for the well being of the animals (BLM, 2023), but scientists consistently disprove these claims (Malone, 2022). Further, scientific studies can be skewed and often show incorrect information in efforts to get public support of roundups. (Nimmo, 2007) (Molvar, 2016)

Current AWH Management

The Bureau and its supporters like to use language surrounding wild horse management like "difficult" and "challenging" (White, 2021), stressing the importance of using easy and long-lasting options even when it's not healthy or humane (HSUS, 2023). This reveals their views of managing wildlife as a chore or unpleasant. Conversely, many other qualified groups enjoy AWH and their habitats and would relish the opportunity to steward their populations.

In response to the largest ever 2022 Strangles (a pathological equine bacterial infection exclusive to those in captivity) outbreak in Cañon City holding facility in Colorado, the CO governor plead with the BLM to stop “rounding up” AWH from public lands, but the BLM ignored his pleas (Brown, 2022). Respectively, Colorado Senators Ginal and Perry, and House Representatives Duran and Lynch have cosponsored a 2023 bill, SB23-275 that proposes...

A wild horse stewardship program is created to help manage range health and infrastructure. The wild horse fertility control program is created to manage the wild horse herd population by collaborating, coordinating, and training people and entities to manage wild horse populations. Both programs are overseen by the wild horse project.

(Direct language from SB23-275)

The bill outlines a state-led management plan in collaboration with the BLM to allot funds and education toward public lands that are habitats for AWH. The Colorado Wild Horse Project, SB23-275 proposes a safe fertility plan to manage AWH populations without removal using helicopters or trapping and to end sterilization of mares. Sterilization is the preferred method of fertility treatment by the BLM because it is permanent (BLM). Sterilization is extremely painful, invasive, traumatic, and dangerous for wild mares, but the safer options are more involved and usually require more than one treatment (HSUS, 2023)(AWHC, 2023).

Friends of a Legacy (FOAL) is a wild horse advocacy group that works with the Bureau to control the populations in McCollough Peaks in Cody, WY. They've successfully managed the wild horse population below the BLM threshold using Porcine Zona Pellucida (PZP) since 1988. PZP is applied into a mare's muscle using a dart. PZP causes the mare's immune system to produce antibodies that block fertilization, but the mare will continue to go into heat (FOAL, 2023). Advocates almost unanimously prefer PZP as a fertility treatment because it is the least invasive option aside from allowing nature to maintain itself.

McCullough Peaks Stallion and Mare, Photo by Sandy Sisti

Compensatory reproduction is an additional issue in AWH population management. Compensatory reproduction happens when horses are rounded up, especially in traumatic events. If part of the herd is removed, the remaining herd members reproduce more quickly to preserve their herd, causing overproduction and weaker foals. (Bradshaw, Jenkins, 2023) This creates a vicious cycle of roundups due to overpopulation and sicknesses in the herd. Natural Selection is therefore prevented, causing disruption to the AWH gene pool. BLM roundups are actually a cause of AWH overpopulation.

The following graphic shows the questionable plans currently proposed by the BLM to manage the Pryor Mountain wild horse herd. They support a 50/50 sex ratio which is grossly incorrect. Horses are harem mating animals (Frankham, 2014), and a 50/50 ratio would result in far too many stallions. This puts not only the gene pool in danger, but it will cause young fillies to be “overbred” (Hellyer, 2023) causing multiple health and herd dynamic issues including death. Notably, reintroduction of natural predators like wolves would bring natural balance to AWH and other population management on BLM managed lands.

MANAGEMENT OBJECTIVES

Specific management, monitoring and implementation objectives are summarized below:

Management Objective(s)	Monitoring Objective(s)	Implementation Objective(s)
<p>A. Population Control</p> <p>Objective 1: Manage wild horse populations within the established AML range (90-120) to protect the range from deterioration associated with overpopulation.</p> <p>Objective 2: Manage wild horse populations to allow for a 5% average growth rate or lower.</p> <p>Objective 3: Adjust the sex ratio of the breeding population to a natural ratio.</p> <p>Objective 4: Gather to the low-range of the AML.</p> <p>Objective 5: Apply fertility control to mares within the JMA to reduce population growth rates below natural rates of approximately 20%.</p>	<p>Annual Population Inventories based on ground counts of wild horses.</p> <p>Determine population number and annual growth rate.</p> <p>Document the number of mares/stallions released following each gather.</p> <p>Conduct post-fertility control monitoring in accordance with established procedures.</p>	<p>Use fertility control measures to achieve and then maintain herd size within AML (RMP MD WH-1). Schedule gathers to remove excess wild horses when the total wild horse population exceeds the AML for the JMA, when animals permanently reside on lands outside the JMA boundaries (i.e. use is more than seasonal drift), or whenever animal health/condition is at risk.</p> <p>Adjust fertility control treatments and removals as needed to allow for the desired average growth rate.</p> <p>Manage a breeding population of 90-120 wild horses. Within the population, achieve a 50%/50% sex ration of males to females immediately following future gathers.</p> <p>Immunocontraceptive use would be conducted in accordance with the approved standard operating and post-treatment monitoring procedures. The fertility control prescription would treat mares ages 2 and 3 with ZonaStat-H. Young mares in the one-year old age class becoming two years old could begin primer treatments in the autumn at 18 months of age but would not be treated before 18 months of age. Mares ages 4 and older would not receive a treatment until after they have successfully foaled once (successfully foaling is defined as a foal living to be 1 year of age). Once a mare has received six consecutive treatments, she would be removed from the fertility control treatment unless she foals again, in which case she would then receive a minimum of three more fertility control treatments or treated with another approved immunocontraceptive. Mares that are non-responders to ZonaStat-H would be treated with another approved immunocontraceptive or removed from the JMA.</p>

Appendices ii-iv contain narrations of three stories for documentation that detail experiences of individual horses as told by the humans who've known them. All of the stories involve different scenarios and reveal problematic areas in BLM management of AWH.

A New Dawn in Ecosystem Management

Land Ethic

Aldo Leopold wrote about heat in the sense of decades as a tree grows and eventually produces heat. He gives an account of everything that happened within the trophic web and of anthropocentric activity in reverse order as he saws through the rings of the tree (Leopold, 1949). This is deep thought that is capable of understanding the complexities of nature and all species within. This type of thinking and feeling can heal the damage done to our ecosystem which is about to break under the stress of abuse and enslavement. To ponder nature is to care for nature. How can one care for nature if one cannot calm their mind enough to listen to a bird sing, or to sit by a brook without planning a road to leave with fruits of the earth? If a person sees oil as blood of the earth rather than fuel, does this make their mind inferior to the one who would clear-cut the forest to sell the wood?

Technology is available to make fuel from sunlight (DOE, 2023) and power from waves using blankets made of recycled plastic (Paleja, 2022). The need for fossil fuel extraction no longer exists making oil land leases unnecessary. Large scale commercial ranching has proven to corrupt the food system (Pollan, 2009), humanity, and the natural balance of nature. Further, cattle ranching that displaces AWH populations privatizes public land and water, and does not serve the US human population any more than it serves the wildlife. A 2022 University of Wyoming analysis found commercial ranching provides less than 1/100th of a percent of wages for people in the

Image courtesy of Department of Energy Office of Science, 2023

United States from CEO to teenage help in feed stores. (Molvar, 2022) European and Scandinavian countries are already switching to renewable energy and rewilding their land (Rewilding Europe, 2023). The majority of young working Americans no longer find it palatable to privatize and exploit others for profit like they did hundreds of years ago. 80% of Americans want to facilitate sustainability for AWH and their habitats on public land (Koshmrl, 2023).

Small changes to the WFRHBA would be ineffective and only enforce the controlling social conditioning to ask for permission from offices like the BLM. Secretary Deb Haaland remains silent regarding all wildlife removal from public lands. Deep systemic change has to happen for our ecosystem to be managed for its future rather than for profit. Scientists and advocates must stop using the language of environmental elitism and use more inclusive language towards the land and all species. With educated management and consideration for the complexity of the land, species communities can repopulate in healthy numbers, creating a complex, healthy ecosystem for the future.

Rewilding in Europe

Europeans are currently re-wilding their ecosystems including their wild horses after their complete and total extermination in 1906. The Europeans have essentially recreated ancient breeds using selective breeding from domesticated horse genetics such as the Konik Polski pony as the recreated Tarpan. (Helmer, 2014). They've also successfully rewilded other breeds like the Serrano horses in the Iberian Highlands of Spain. The rewilded herds are becoming well-established, and

three foals were born in 2022. Rewilding Europe is a fairly new environmental group and has already established a healthy natural grazing threshold by introducing grazing communities of horses, buffalo, red deer and fallow deer, and the Kulan, a wild donkey species. The grazers use niche partitioning which has increased plant diversity and animal biodiversity in the rewilded areas. Low intensity natural grazing also reduces wild fire risk. (Rewilding Europe, 2023)

Europeans consider the wild horse a keystone species. Image courtesy of Rewilding Europe

Reserve Design

Craig Downer, Wild Horse Ecologist

Craig Downer is a wild horse ecologist and has developed Reserve Design as a sustainable management practice for wild horses on public lands. Downer acknowledges that AWH are “highly evolved, and anciently rooted and long standing” species of this land and prays “their destiny should not be to remain forever the mere slaves of humans.” They “play keystone roles that enhance and embellish” their ecosystem and should be appreciated as such. Reserve Design is akin to rewilding and joins modern conservation science and restoration of knowledge with respect for wildlife. Key elements are outlined below:

- Careful study of the ecosystem in question including both natural and human components
 - Incorporation of natural barriers such as high mountains, deep canyons, and rivers to act as limits to wild equid expansion into unsafe or undesirable areas
 - Where deemed necessary, construction of semipermeable, artificial barriers such as buck rail or log-pole fences
 - Established “buffer zones” with the cooperation of local landowners and government agencies at all levels
 - Reintroduction and restoration of natural predators of AWH and burros such as pumas, bears, and wolves
 - Patience and facility for horse and burro populations to fill their respective ecological niches and naturally self-stabilize within their habitats
 - Educate the public with programs about healthy biodiversity and the role of wild horses within the ecosystem
 - Relationship development between wild horse herds and the local community through community outreach that are non-disruptive to the animals
 - Facilitation of field biology classes at all education levels to observe wild horses
- Incorporate steps to eventually loosen the present stranglehold and monopolization of public lands

Downer speaks of the importance of allowing wild horses to decompose naturally on their land after their death. “It is only right and natural that (their) remains should be used by all other species, from plants to animals to decomposers who go together to form each unique and interconnected ecosystem.” Downer works extensively with the Apache-Sitgreaves wild horses and suggests a study using the herd to develop more data for future management. Water seems to be the key component to wildlife health. All ecosystem health from the forage cascading up to the apex is directly dependent on plentiful, clean water (Westlind, 2018).

A rare, unbiased study of grasses and grazing areas from U of Alaska Fairbanks concludes that “ungulate animals benefit ecosystems by enriching soil, spreading seeds, and helping grasslands become vibrant.” (Westlind, 2018) A study in Argentina concludes that “avian richness and diversity were higher in areas subject to moderate levels of grazing than areas in which horses had been excluded.” (Zalba, Cozzani, 2004). Introducing different species as a natural rotational grazing community enhances the forage biodiversity and strengthens root systems of naturally growing plants on the range. Controlled burns create greater nutrient density in forage (Rayner, 2016) and help to control invasive species (Miller, 1983) and unexpected fire risk (Rewilding Europe, 2023).

Tribal Co-Management of Federal Public Lands

Kevin Washburn

Former Assistant Secretary, Bureau of Indian Affairs

Dean, University of Iowa College of Law

“Native American tribal nations enter hundreds of federal contracts worth billions of dollars every year (Washburn, 2022).” Indigenous people/Native Americans wish to co-manage public lands and have “traditional ecological knowledge and practices regarding resource management that have been passed down through generations (Secretary of the Interior, 2006).” Tribes have been managing federal programs for roughly 40 years since the passage of the 1988 Amendments that allowed Native council to enter into contracts with the BLM and other federal agencies.

Indigenous people have gained the experience needed to negotiate contracts with government agencies through years of experience. They've learned and understand the missions of these federal offices and have gained government trust with federal programs. After being rejected or having their contracts delayed or cancelled, native councils eventually won small contracts and worked their way upwards to managing federal lands for the government to "sustain the health, diversity, and productivity of America's public land for the use and enjoyment of present and future generations" as per the BLM mission statement. "There is no doubt that tribes frequently have centuries-old and symbiotic relationships with various species (Washburn, 2022)" and have strong sustainable management of wildlife.

In 2005, the BLM initially resisted negotiations with the Council of Athabascan Tribal Government (CATG) in rural Alaska for a contract to fight fires on the grounds that fire-fighting had no significance to the tribal community. The CATG convinced the BLM "that fires are part of the natural resource system in which subsistence and other cultural patterns are embedded." The BLM first rejected the proposed budget then delayed sending it to Congress. The BLM eventually "proposed a take-it-or-leave it \$4000 contract" (Washburn, 2022) for the native tribes to teach them to fight fires in 2006.

Jason and Patti Baldes who are Shoshone and Arapahoe, respectively, manage a large buffalo population on the Wind River Reservation in Wyoming. They also manage formerly wild horses with a BLM private holding contract and have a separate herd for themselves (Lezak, 2021). They've found an intriguing symbiosis between Native culture and federal government culture where buffalo are repopulating, and wild horses have sanctuary within tribal boundaries.

"The effort began with a partnership between the two tribes, the National Wildlife Federation and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. Jason (Baldes) led the work wearing two hats; he's both the National Wildlife Federation's tribal buffalo coordinator and the Shoshone tribal buffalo representative. In 2016, the first buffalo were given a home in a small

enclosure owned by the Shoshone Tribe. Three years later, the Arapaho Tribe acquired its own herd.”

—Lezak for High Country News, 2021

“Wild horses and buffalo share a lot of the social-economic-political journey in this country, and when you overlay that with the plight of Indigenous people, you get this triad” said Baldes. He later added “Cows are invasive species. Just don’t call them that, because ‘cattle is king’ in Wyoming.” Tribal management for government agencies brings a nexus of expertise, commitment, and resources to projects that the government doesn’t always provide. Indigenous people have a deep connection to the land and are willing to manage for sustainability. Tribal councils had to learn strategic thinking to gain contracts with the government as most of the resistance to tribal co-management has been political. Tribal councils have learned to “meet the agency’s missions better than the agency itself. (Washburn, 2022)”

Tribal co-management already exists in federal law and requires no significant new congressional action (Washburn, 2022). Tribes have been seeking much more meaningful roles in the management of public lands and working more with “green groups” like The Sierra Club, The Audubon Society, and The Center for Biodiversity. Tribal governments are well-situated to engage in federal public land management. With 44 million acres, collectively, tribes are the sixth largest owner of land in the United States (Washburn, 2022).

Private Acquisition of Land for Wildlife Management

American Wild Horse Campaign

Many privately owned sanctuaries exist for formerly wild horses and burros like Skydog Ranch in Oregon, The CANA Foundation in New York, and Wild Horse Haven in Arizona. American Wild Horse Campaign, similar to FOAL in Wyoming and the Cloud Foundation in Colorado, maintains land for preservation of its natural existence, focusing on wild and often endangered species. AWHC recently acquired 3,300 acres of land in the Carson Valley of Nevada near the BLM run Pine Nut Valley AWH habitat.

The new AWHC land is home to many native species including wild horses and has 40 acres of freshwater available to the animals year round.

The Carson Valley land acquisition is part of a pilot program to conserve undeveloped lands and preserve AWH herds in Nevada. AWHC works with the Pine Nut Wild Horse Advocates administering PZP fertility control to AWH. Although PZP is controversial to conservationists, it seems the least invasive option due to human encroachment on public lands (HSUS, 2022). Combining legal expertise with land ownership, AWHCs conservation program ensures their wild lands will be kept safe from harassment by the federal government. AWHC is attempting to obtain stewardship contracts with federal and local governments for AWH on conserved land (AWHC, 2023).

Efforts by the AWHC are funded through their legal practices and donations acquired using social media to raise awareness of AWH controversy and AWHC efforts to protect AWH populations.

Conclusion

AWH are a native species that are mismanaged by the federal government which is harmful, not only to AWH and the ecosystem, but to the humanity of Americans as well. Taxonomy of the horse is an early indicator of misrepresentation of the species that has been exacerbated throughout American colonial history. AWH have deep connections to North American land and its people. Several methods of preservation and population management are presented in this thesis with different levels of cooperation with the federal government. Popular opinion is that public land management should be decentralized from the seemingly archaic stronghold of the BLM, and community input should become more important in creating sustainable and morally sound care for AWH and their habitat.

American public lands are indeed becoming scarce with increased human population. Maximizing nutrition from forage and fresh water retention in public spaces

would be most helpful in managing AWH and other grazing ungulates moving forward. A cap on cattle ranching and condensing of leasing permits on public lands are two responsible options to begin the conversation of conservation of federally controlled land. Tribal council can be of great help as traditional methods of land management will become more important as natural resources become scarce and more native species become endangered due to carelessness of the American people. Efforts to keep public lands accessible to all people and wild animals is of utmost importance in the 21st century.

Appendix i

Phylogenetic reconstructions portray historic and modern North American horses as mainly descending from domestic bloodlines that started spreading outside their native area of the Don-Volga region no earlier than 4200 years ago (Librado, 2021)

(A) Y-Fig. 2. Phylogenetic affinities. chromosomal maximum-likelihood tree ($N = 110$; 5244 nucleotide transversions). (B) Mitochondrial maximum-likelihood tree ($N = 340$; 16,406 base pairs). (C) Neighbor-joining tree based on ~7.5 million nucleotide transversions ($N = 241$; left), and the corresponding genetic ancestry profiles (right). The ancestry proportions for $K = 7$ genetic components were estimated using Struc-f4. Sample names written as “OGLAKO/ Apache” represent modern North American horses culturally associated with Apache communities. LP, Late Pleistocene; ELEN, *Equus lenensis* (Siberia); DOM2, modern domestic lineage descending from a lower Don-Volga genetic source expanding to Eurasia after 4200 years ago. (Taylor, 2023)

Appendix ii

Atsa's Story

Burns, Oregon

Told by Stephanie Bradshaw

Atsa himself was not captured by the helicopter roundup in the South Steens in Oregon, but his herd mates were. He refused to leave them in the pen even though he was free and was then roped and captured by some of the handlers. Agents of the BLM beat Atsa and whipped him, and Atsa watched his herd mates die that day. It was an especially brutal round up (helicopters chase wild horses into a pen for removal from the land), and 35 horses died of broken necks, backs, and legs (AWHC). An unusually large number of foals were trampled or died from shock

during this particular round up. Atsa was castrated, allegedly without anesthesia, and freeze branded on his neck. Atsa was then left in a short term holding pen for around 2 years before he was deemed adoptable and purchased by a Missouri trainer through the Adoption Incentive Program (AIP). Atsa was now 28 years old but mistakenly branded as much younger.

Freezebrand used by the BLM

Atsa is an extremely tall horse that had been traumatized, beaten, and tortured during capture after living wild for over 20 years. None of this was disclosed to the unknowing adopter. The adopter runs a small horse farm and adopted Atsa in hopes of training him for riding lessons. She couldn't work with him. She tried "what she knew" but was unsuccessful and eventually gave up, leaving him locked in a round pen for over a year and a half. He wanted nothing to do with humans. He was terrified and traumatized. He wasn't eating, his hooves weren't trimmed, and his pen was not cleaned for over a year and a half. He was also isolated with no contact from other horses or humans.

When Atsa's rescuer, Stephanie, discovered him, she immediately insisted the adopter allow her to work with Atsa. The adopter at first refused, but Stephanie insisted. After 90 minutes of intense concentration and trust building, Stephanie was able to get him to eat some alfalfa that she threw to him from across the pen. The adopter said this was the first time she'd seen Atsa eat.

Atsa in a miserable state due to negligence

Stephanie continued to work with Atsa successfully until the current owner, his adopter, ran out of funds and exhausted her efforts to take care of him. The adopter suggested to sell Atsa for slaughter, but Stephanie offered to take him to her quarantine pen until she could find him a suitable home. Stephanie worked with Atsa and gained his trust. She rehabilitated him back to health and eventually found Skydog

Atsa at Skydog Sanctuary, 2023

Wild Horse Sanctuary and created a fundraiser to bring Atsa back to Oregon. Skydog Sanctuary, amazingly, is adjacent to Atsa's wild home and has the facilities to safely contain a horse as tall as Atsa.

After 5 years of being away, when Stephanie and Atsa passed by the holding pen where Atsa was first held, Atsa called out to his herd mates. He knew where he was, and he knew his herd was still there. His arrival at Skydog was quite tearful as they'd never seen a horse so big or so traumatized. Claire at Skydog knew exactly what to do and brought Atsa a friend right away. Atsa has now been integrated into his new herd at Skydog and lives with 2 of his wild herd mates. It was very emotional to watch his transformation back to being "wild."

Atsa was rescued from the horrible fate of thousands of horses per year. His adoption through the AIP is a BLM program to encourage wild horse adoptions. Adopters are paid \$500 immediately after adoption and \$500 one year later if the horse is in good body condition. Surprisingly though, there is no pre-screening process for the adopters and no check back by the BLM, even though that is part of the AIP contract. In Atsa's case, he was left living in the dark, standing in his own feces with no food for over a year and a half until he was accidentally discovered by his rescuer, Stephanie. Once Atsa was ready for his journey, Stephanie contacted the BLM to have him titled before she turned him over to

sanctuary. The BLM responded saying that his title and the second \$500 check had already been sent to the adopter in Missouri. When Stephanie asked who signed the body condition certification papers, the BLM replied that she did. Upon viewing the papers, the adopter had forged Stephanie's signature. Stephanie was never notified that her name was being used as a credential in the program. Atsa's original adopter had 3 other AIP horses on her farm.

Had Atsa not been adopted, he would have been sold at auction and entered the slaughter pipeline which is a string of auctions reaching from Canada to Mexico. This is a dark underworld of horse trade and slaughter fueled by manipulative Facebook users, among others, and extreme neglect by the BLM. Part of the AIP is a promise not to sell the adopted Mustang to slaughter, but there are no repercussions for anyone who does, leading to mass deaths and "kill buyers" who make millions, adopting and selling wild horses at auction.

Appendix iii

Survivor's story

Bend, Oregon

Larry McFerrin and his wife live in Oregon near the South Steens wild horse herd. The McFerrins came to know these horses through walking and photography. At first Larry enjoyed capturing the horses in exquisite photos, but he gradually got to know these wild animals and came to understand them. They became accustomed to seeing them, and now the horses are infused into their lives. Larry has spent a lot of time with the wild horses, and he says they “just reach into your chest and grab a hold a your heart.”

Larry found newborn Survivor in some brush and named him because he was born premature and survived in the harsh environment against all odds. The conditions of the South Steens area are very dry with difficult terrain and direct sun. It's not an ecosystem that supports fragile organisms. Survivor was 2 years old when he was rounded up, and Larry remembers that he had “just come into his own and was acting like a bachelor.”

Baby Survivor, photos by Larry McFerrin

The traps were set the night before, and Larry and his wife saw Survivor within a mile of the trap, a temporary holding corral with a chute made of equine gates, set up by the BLM. Survivor's herd was rounded up by helicopters the next day, September

11th, 2022, and the last known photo of Survivor was of him in the chute to the trap. It was posted to Facebook by Angi Harmon-Wise but quickly removed and has since been denied to exist. The handlers didn't want anyone to see or hear what was happening in the traps. Survivor's herd was trailered and driven to the Burns holding facility in Bend, Oregon (after a quick stop at Safeway) where they were sorted, tagged, and freeze-branded.

22 horses were executed that day even though it was clearly against BLM regulations to "euthanize a horse in short term holding unless it is in extreme pain (BLM 2023)" Short-term holding corral management can create a Permanent Instruction Memorandum, so the WFRHBA can be overridden by BLM holding facilities at will. "It's amazing how convoluted (the WFRHBA) has become" McFerrin said. Eleven of the 22 executed horses were Cremellos (AWHC) which was Survivor's phenotype. No one knows exactly why they were shot, and all of the FOIA requests are currently unanswered. The owner/manager of Burns holding facility (his name has been changed to Bob for purposes of this account.) does have a reputation for being somewhat narrow-minded**. One advocate was shocked when they heard about the "Cremello Incident" as it is now called. "He used to be so proud of his corral and how he took care of his horses," they said. Upon psychological evaluation of public, online testimony, it seems that Bob has become corrupted due to the warden-like status he holds over wild animals as an unwanted commodity. "Oppression — overwhelming control — is necrophilic; it is nourished by love of death, not life." (Friere, 1970)

"And the more the oppressors control the oppressed, the more they change them into apparently inanimate "things." This tendency of the oppressor consciousness to "in-animate" everything and everyone it encounters, in its eagerness to possess, unquestionably corresponds with a tendency to Sadism... —a love of death, not of life. One of the characteristics of the oppressor consciousness and its necrophilic view of the world is thus sadism."

— Paulo Friere, Pedagogy of the Oppressed, 1970

Bob also has a known dislike for Cremellos for reasons unknown to the locals. One could reasonably deduce, however, in his Lebensbornesque program, he manages his corral for pinto coloring, and pinto coloring is turned creme by the dominant dilute creme gene present in Cremellos. The genetics of the Cremello phenotype will always cause pinto coloring not to show, even if pinto is present in the genes of the offspring. This would also explain why palomino-colored pintos are now an acceptable phenotype in the Burns holding facility at the BLM (BLM, 2023).

Bob lied and said the horses were blind the day they were “euthanized,” but they were not blind. The horses were observed by McFerrin and other wild horse photographers for years and less than 24 hours before the helicopter roundup of their herd. A wild horse rescue offered to adopt them (AWHC 2022), but Bob and his private veterinarian decided to “euthanized them immediately” rather than adopt them out. Multiple people have filed dozens of FOIA requests asking questions about what happened to the Cremellos and why. All FOIAs but one are unanswered. McFerrin received a letter from the BLM veterinarian which vaguely stated that horses who are blind are euthanized on site for their own well being, “a necessity for their own safety in a new environment.” The letter did not directly address any horse or any direct action by the BLM. So many people are distraught over this heinous act and cover-up that there is an active support page on Facebook called The Survivor Project, headed by Larry McFerrin.

Oddly enough, the bodies of the 11 Cremellos are unaccounted for, so this story really is a mystery.

Survivor, by Larry McFerrin

**For the protection of all involved in this story, it's imperative to note that no one has said anything or printed anything about "Bob." The author and narrator of this true account did their own research through private connections and public online searches and believes these ideas are true. No one from any rescue or anywhere in Oregon or surrounding areas have given any testimony at all against Bob.

Val, Brown Stallion, and Creme (Norman). A great photo by Gulliermo Avila Paz.
“Hey Brother, You got the wrong Lens”

Appendix iv

Guillermo, Val, and Creme

Onaqui, Utah

Guillermo is originally from Bolivia and moved to the US as a kid. He went to high school in Idaho but was expelled for being “Mexican” and “not Mormon” of all things. His father moved him across the country, and he became an Olympic skier for the United States. After a ski accident in Park City Utah, Guillermo relocated close to the Onaqui range where he met Val. Val brought Guillermo to the Onaqui desert to heal. The two men had photography in common and spent a lot of time on the Onaqui range photographing horses, wild birds, and the stars. Guillermo became acquainted with the Onaqui wild horses in this way and sells his fine arts photography of them in a gallery in Park City Utah. He discovered a newborn foal that he named Creme. Guillermo and Val continued to visit Creme and watched him grow. Creme quickly became a herd favorite with advocates who called him Norman. He was unusually friendly to humans to the delight of photographers.

Guillermo was present on Onaqui Mountain outside of Salt Lake City, UT when the BLM decided to round up 800/1700 of the Onaqui wild herd in 2019. He was visibly upset as he filmed them removing the horses from the range in metal trailers. The horses could be heard crying as they passed by. It was distressing to watch, and honestly would make anyone feel angry. This video is significant because it's one of the few ever published from this distance since the BLM doesn't usually allow people to record what they're doing. Soon after, the land was occupied by a wealthy cattle baron, an heir to the Mormon church who used the land for cattle ranching.

Guillermo explained that the horses have a deeply organized social system. There are two main stallions and one head mare. The entire herd follows the mare, and she is the one who knows how to get water, forage, and minerals from the ground. Without this mare, and without the two stallions who look over the herd, "the herd is done." Helicopter roundups don't respect herd dynamics or what advocates call "the nucleus of the herd." (Mustang Meg)

"The horses were my therapy. (The BLM) took my therapy. . . all to please ranchers." When Guillermo's friend, Val heard what had happened, the two visited the now empty range. Val went home and took his own life that evening leaving behind his wife and his friend to make sense of it all. Guillermo is currently a plaintiff in *Amelia Arcamone-Makinano, et al. V the Bureau of Land Management in Utah* for the illegal removal of horses from public lands for private interest.

Baby Creme (Norman)

Grown Creme (Norman) and his band. Norman was “euthanized” in 2022 by the BLM due to an injury.

In Memoriam

This thesis is written in memoriam of the horses who have lost their lives or their freedom during the time the thesis was written:

Jasper and his bay stallion friend, shot in the night at close range on Onaqui public lands in April 2023. A third horse was reported missing the same morning. There's been no investigation into possible suspects.

Bunny and family who were lured onto public property and removed in February 2023 by the BLM and its supporters. This family has since been separated and all of their whereabouts are unknown .

Blondie and his band who were removed from the Pine Nut area in March 2023 by the BLM. One horse was left behind who chased the trailer that carried his family from their lands. (No reason has been stated for their removal.) Blondie has been gelded and separated from his band. They're currently being held at Palomino Valley.

31 burros who died in Aug/Sept 2022 in short term BLM holding. 25 deaths were from hyperlipidemia, an infection from not eating, and 6 burros died due to infection from gelding by the BLM.

The horses and burros who died of the 2022 Strangles outbreak in Wyoming and those who are dying right now of the April 2023 Strangles outbreak in California.

The countless others who were sold at auction into the slaughter pipeline, and to those waiting in kill pens or otherwise incarcerated by the US government.

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(Mackay)

Personal Communications:

Ross Mac Phee, Paleontologist, New York, Feb 2023

Larry Mc Ferrin, Oregon AWH Photographer, Nov 2022

Gulliermo Avila Paz, Park City Utah, Onaqui herd, March 2023

Stephanie Bradshaw, Steph K Equestrian, March 2023

Heather Hellyer, Save Our Wild Horses, Aug 2022 – Present

Erik Molvar, Western Watershed Project, Aug 2022

Linda Greaves, Save Our Wild Horses, March 2023

Penny Jackson, Florida, AWH Advocate, March 2023

Scott Beckstead, Oregon, February 2023

Mike Jenkins, Kansas, AWH Advocate, AIP Expert, March 2023

Stephanie Big Eagle, Sacred Horse Society, March 2023

Burros have been homogenized into AWH communities and are threatened with constant removals by the government. Please take a moment to reflect on this often forgotten keystone species of the American West.

Photos courtesy of American Wild Horse Campaign

